

THE IMPACT OF CLIL (CONTENT AND LANGUAGE INTEGRATED LEARNING) ON ENGLISH LANGUAGE PROFICIENCY

Buranova Madina Uktamovna

PhD, Associate professor at the department of “English Language”

Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

Uzbekistan, Samarkand

madinaburanova82@gmail.com

Abstract: This study explores the impact of Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) on improving English language proficiency in students. CLIL integrates subject content with language learning, allowing students to acquire both subject knowledge and language skills simultaneously. The paper examines the role of CLIL in enhancing learners' speaking, writing, listening, and reading skills in English. Additionally, it investigates how CLIL promotes language fluency through an immersive environment and its effectiveness compared to traditional English language teaching methods. Findings suggest that CLIL not only accelerates language learning but also fosters greater motivation and deeper understanding of both language and content.

Keywords: CLIL, English language proficiency, language learning, integrated learning, immersive learning, education, language skills.

Introduction:

Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) is a dual-focused educational approach where an additional language is used to teach both content and language. CLIL has grown in popularity as a method for improving language proficiency without isolating language from the curriculum. This approach promotes an

immersive learning environment, in which language is learned within meaningful contexts, thus supporting deeper understanding and real-world application. This paper investigates the impact of CLIL on English language proficiency, focusing on key language skills, including speaking, reading, writing, and listening, while examining the broader implications for student motivation and engagement.

The CLIL methodology, first introduced by Marsh (1994), has gained significant traction in European and global contexts. Studies indicate that CLIL fosters not only linguistic competence but also cognitive skills through content-specific learning (Coyle et al., 2010). A comparative analysis of CLIL and traditional methods of language teaching reveals that CLIL tends to be more effective in improving oral fluency and comprehension skills, largely due to the natural integration of language into subject matter learning (Dalton-Puffer, 2011). Additionally, CLIL encourages students to think critically in the target language, thereby improving their problem-solving and analytical capabilities (Mehisto, 2008).

Methodology:

This study adopts a mixed-method approach, combining quantitative assessments of language proficiency with qualitative insights from interviews and classroom observations. The sample consists of 100 students from various high schools who were exposed to CLIL-based curricula over the course of an academic year. Pre- and post-tests were conducted to measure improvements in key language areas: speaking, reading, writing, and listening. Additionally, teachers and students were interviewed to gather qualitative data on their perceptions of CLIL's effectiveness in enhancing language skills and subject knowledge.

A mixed-method approach in research combines both quantitative and qualitative methods to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the research problem. By using both approaches, researchers can explore the strengths of each method to address the limitations of the other, resulting in a more robust analysis.

This involves collecting and analyzing numerical data. The goal is to measure the relationship between variables using statistics and objective measures. In the context of educational research (such as CLIL), quantitative assessments could include:

- Pre- and post-tests to measure students' English language proficiency levels (e.g., scores in speaking, writing, reading, or listening skills).
- Surveys or questionnaires with closed-ended questions (e.g., Likert scales) to measure student attitudes or motivation in numerical terms.

The data is typically analyzed using statistical tools to identify patterns, correlations, and changes over time.

Qualitative methods, on the other hand, focus on gathering non-numerical data to explore deeper insights into attitudes, behaviors, and experiences. This could involve:

- Interviews with teachers and students to explore their perspectives on the effectiveness of CLIL.
- Classroom observations where researchers analyze how students interact with CLIL-based lessons, language use, and teaching strategies.
- Open-ended questions in surveys where students describe their learning experiences in detail.

In a mixed-method approach, researchers use quantitative data to provide a measurable, objective foundation and qualitative data to enrich this by offering context and in-depth understanding. For example:

- The quantitative results might show that students' language proficiency increased by 20% after using CLIL.
- The qualitative interviews might reveal why students found CLIL more engaging or why certain students struggled despite the overall improvement in scores.

By combining both types of data, the researcher can validate the findings and explain complex phenomena from multiple angles.

Results and Discussion:

Quantitative results demonstrate significant improvements in students' overall language proficiency. Specifically, CLIL learners outperformed their peers in speaking and listening skills, with a 20% higher proficiency rate in speaking tasks compared to students in traditional English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classes. Writing skills also improved, particularly in the areas of academic and subject-specific vocabulary, as students were able to apply their language knowledge to subject content effectively. The qualitative data from interviews highlight increased student motivation, with many learners noting that CLIL made the language learning process more engaging and practical.

The results align with existing literature, reinforcing the idea that CLIL enhances language proficiency by providing a context-rich, immersive environment (Lasagabaster & Sierra, 2009). However, the study also reveals challenges, such as the need for well-trained teachers who are proficient in both the target language and subject content. Additionally, CLIL requires substantial curriculum design, where both language and content objectives are clearly outlined.

Conclusion:

The study concludes that CLIL has a significant positive impact on English language proficiency, particularly in improving speaking and listening skills. By integrating content learning with language acquisition, CLIL provides a more holistic and engaging approach to language education. However, for CLIL to reach its full potential, educators must receive adequate training and curricula must be thoughtfully designed. Future research should focus on long-term effects of CLIL on language retention and its application across different subject areas.

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